

Zitterbewegung in Statistical Systems with Space Dependent Potentials?

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In a number of notes [2]-[9], a linear 2x2 matrix Dirac type equation was examined as a solution of Einstein's 1905 energy momentum equation $E^2=p^2+m^2$ (1). This model was able to reproduce Schrodinger zitterbewegung.[1] To do this, however, one had to identify the 2x2 energy matrix H as being part of the evolution operator $\exp(-iHt)$. It was seen that the identity matrix together with H could transform any two vector into the eigenvector of H, which is taken as the stable solution. This idea of an evolution operator thus seems to be important.

In addition, the model led to a 2-eigenvector which was interpreted as the square root of two components of probability, one in which a particle moves forward the other in which it moves backward Overall, the particle moves forward with a velocity of v along the x axis. Knuth [18] has also proposed such a model. It was found that the probabilities which came from this quantum mechanical type matrix solution matched those obtained by maximizing statistical entropy. In a note [22], the 2x2 matrix model was applied to a system of classical particles which could have energy e_1 or e_2 . It was argued that the 2x2 model predicted zitterbewegung for this statistical system. The object of this note is to explore whether the 2x2 model can be used to predict zitterbewegung in a statistical system with a potential.

Statistical System with a Potential

In statistical mechanics books, E the kinetic energy is replaced with $E+V$, in distributions, such as the Maxwell-Boltzmann, when a potential exists. Alternative derivations consider a little box of mass at r_0 acted on by a force $-\text{grad}V$. The difference in pressure at r_+ and r_- balance this force, leading to equilibrium.

Pressure is given by: $\frac{1}{3} S dp p f(p)v(p)$ where $f(p)$ is the distribution in question, v velocity and p the momentum.

,The presence of a potential $V(r)$ creates unequal density in a statistical system. For the case of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-V(r)/T)$ describes how the density varies with r.

2x2 Matrix Model

In this statistical case, we do not have a starting equation such as Einstein's energy momentum equation (1). We can, however, ask whether a 2x2 matrix model will apply. In such a case, the 2-eigenvector would describe $\sqrt{\exp(-V(r_+)/T)}$ and $\sqrt{\exp(-V(r_-)/T)}$ Square roots of probabilities appear in the 2x2 quantum mechanical like model. In addition, one would need a matrix associated with the eigenvector. This matrix already exists. If one normalizes the

probabilities at r_+ and r_- then the eigenvector is $(\cos(a/2), \sin(a/2))$, the eigenvalue 1 and the matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \cos(a) & \sin(a) \\ \sin(a) & -\cos(a) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

At this point, one may ask if there is any motivation for choosing such a matrix? It has been shown in [2]-[9] that this matrix (2) together with the identity matrix can convert any 2 vector into the eigenvector. In particular, if there were no potential $V(r)$, the 2 vector describing the situation would be $(1,1)$. There would be no difference in probability to be at r_+ or r_- . With a potential $V(r)$, $(1,1)$ would transform into $(\sqrt{\exp(-V(r_+)/T)}, \sqrt{\exp(-V(r_-)/T)})$. If r_+ and r_- are close, the difference in the square root of the probabilities should be small. In the limit of this difference being very small, the matrix (2) should become a matrix with eigenvector $(1,1)$ i.e.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Let us examine this in more detail.

$$\cos(a/2) = \frac{\exp(-V(r_+)/2T)}{\sqrt{[\exp(-V(r_+)/T) + \exp(-V(r_-)/T)']}}$$

$$\text{and } \sin(a/2) = \frac{\exp(-V(r_-)/2T)}{\sqrt{[\exp(-V(r_+)/T) + \exp(-V(r_-)/T)']}}$$

Then $\cos(a) = \cos^2(a/2) - \sin^2(a/2)$ which is proportional to $\text{Prob}(r_+) - \text{Prob}(r_-)$ which is proportional to the difference in pressure. This difference in pressure may be small if $-\text{grad}(V(r))$ is small.

$\sin(a) = 2\cos(a/2)\sin(a/2)$ on the other hand is proportional to $\exp(-V(r_0)/T)$ which is proportional to the mass of a little box at r_0 . Thus, the matrix (2) is related to the matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Delta(\text{Pressure}) & \text{mass} \\ \text{mass} & -\Delta(\text{Pressure}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

For $\Delta(\text{Pressure})$ being very small we obtain (3) with eigenvector $(1,1)$ yielding equal probabilities. Thus, it seems that the 2×2 matrix can describe a statistical system with a potential, at least to a certain degree.

The next item to identify is a constraint matrix. In this case, $\text{Pressure}(r_+) - \text{Pressure}(r_-) = -\text{grad}(V(r)) \text{mass}(r_0)$. Pressure is proportional to probability f so the constraint can be written as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{f_1} & \sqrt{f_2} \\ \sqrt{f_1} & -\sqrt{f_2} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Thus } P = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ can serve as a constraint matrix.}$$

Let us consider the matrix (4) as the sum of (3) and the constraint matrix multiplied by b, a small amount. Now $\exp(-V(r+)/2T) = \exp(-V(r_0)/2T) [1 + b/2]$ where $b = \Delta(V) \Delta(r)$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1+b/2 \\ 1-b/2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1-b/2 \\ 1+b/2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The constraint matrix multiplied by b gives:

$$\begin{bmatrix} b & 0 \\ 0 & -b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1+b/2 \\ 1-b/2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b \\ b \end{bmatrix}$$

Adding the two results gives $\begin{bmatrix} 1+b/2 \\ 1-b/2 \end{bmatrix}$ which is equivalent to $\begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{\exp(-V(r+)/2T)} \\ \sqrt{\exp(-V(r-)/2T)} \end{bmatrix}$

Zitterbewegung

The 2x2 matrix approach then allows for the calculation of zitterbewegung using:

$$P(t) = \text{pressure matrix in time} = \exp(iHt) P \exp(-iHt)$$

Now the H we have chosen has eigenvalues of 1 and -1. In general, one would have eigenvalues of $\pm w$. In the case of the Einstein energy momentum equation, the eigenvalues were $\pm E$ where E was the energy. Here we will write w for our eigenvalue.

$$P(t) = \cos^2(wt) P + i \sin(wt)\cos(wt) [H, P] + \sin^2(wt) HPH$$

$$P(t) = \cos^2(wt) P + i \sin(wt)\cos(wt) 2\sin(a) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \sin^2(wt) \begin{bmatrix} \cos a & -\sin a \\ -\sin a & -\cos a \end{bmatrix}$$

Where $\cos(a) = [\exp(-V(r+)/T) - \exp(-V(r-)/T)] / [\exp(-V(r+)/T) + \exp(-V(r-)/T)]$

And $\sin(a) = 2 \exp(-V(r+)/2T)\exp(-V(r-)/2T) / [\exp(-V(r+)/T) + \exp(-V(r-)/T)]$

This suggests that even though on average the pressure at r+ and r- compensates the force times the mass at r0, there are periodic fluctuations occurring in pressure.

It was earlier argued [23], that one could describe the density of a gas rotating in a cylinder in terms of a Schrodinger equation with $\sqrt{\text{density}}$ as the wavefunction. It was argued that the density in the system might be produced by sound waves which were described in a quantum

mechanical formalism. The zitterbewegung here might suggest the same. The statistical system has a varying density due to the potential $V(r)$, but there may be oscillations creating this density distribution.

Conclusion

In this note we have applied a 2x2 Dirac like quantum mechanical model, originally developed as a way of solving Einstein's energy momentum equation (1) to a statistical mechanical system with a space dependent potential. We have considered densities at $r+$ and $r-$ two positions very close to each other and have used these two densities in the two vector of the model. We have tried to argue that an energy type matrix can act as an evolution operator and have showed how it acts on an eigenvector made up of square root of the probability at $r+$ and $r-$. As a next step, we have calculated zitterbewegung and have argued that it might describe physical density oscillations in the system, such as sound waves, which may be dynamically creating the density distribution.

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